

1 **Gas chromatography-Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization-Time**
2 **of Flight Mass spectrometry for profiling of phenolic compounds in**
3 **extra virgin olive oil**
4

5 **Rocío García-Villalba^{1#}, Tiziana Pacchiarotta^{2#}, Alegría Carrasco-Pancorbo¹,**
6 **Antonio Segura-Carretero¹, Alberto Fernández-Gutiérrez¹, André M. Deelder²,**
7 **Oleg A. Mayboroda^{2*}.**

8 ¹Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, University of Granada, c/ Fuentenueva s/n,
9 E-18071 Granada, Spain.

10 ²LUMC, Biomolecular Mass Spectrometry Unit, Department of Parasitology, Leiden, The Netherlands.

11

12 [#] Those authors contributed equally to this manuscript.

13

14 ^{*}Corresponding author:

15 Dr. Oleg A. Mayboroda

16 LUMC, Biomolecular Mass Spectrometry Unit, Department of Parasitology, Leiden,
17 The Netherlands.

18 **E-mail:** O.A.Mayboroda@lumc.nl.

19 **Fax:** +31-71-526-6907

20

21

22

23 **ABSTRACT**

24

25 A new analytical approach based on gas chromatography coupled to atmospheric
26 pressure chemical ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry was evaluated for its
27 applicability for the analysis of phenolic compounds from extra-virgin olive oil.. Both
28 chromatographic and MS parameters were optimized in order to improve the sensitivity
29 and to maximize the number of phenolic compounds detected. We performed a
30 complete analytical validation of the method with respect to its linearity, sensitivity,
31 precision, accuracy and possible matrix effects. The LODs ranged from 0.13 to 1.05
32 ppm for the different tested compounds depending on their properties. The RSDs for
33 repeatability test did not exceed 6.07% and the accuracy ranged from 95.4% to 101.5%.
34 To demonstrate the feasibility of our method for analysis of real samples, we analyzed
35 the extracts of three different commercial extra-virgin olive oils. We have identified
36 unequivocally a number of phenolic compounds and obtained quantitative information
37 for 21 of them.

38 In general, our results show that GC-APCI-TOF MS is a flexible platform which can be
39 considered as an interesting tool for screening, structural assignment and quantitative
40 determination of phenolic compounds from virgin olive oil.

41

42

43 **Keywords:** Gas chromatography / Mass spectrometry / Atmospheric Pressure Chemical
44 Ionization / Phenolic compounds / Olive oil

45 **1. Introduction**

46 The beneficial effects of the Mediterranean diet on human health such as reducing the
47 risk of atherosclerosis, cardiovascular diseases and certain types of cancer are proven
48 facts [1,2]. The dietary consumption of virgin olive oil (VOO) by Mediterranean
49 populations is believed to play a key role in this health protective phenomenon.
50 Historically, the health protecting properties of VOO have been ascribed to the high
51 proportion of monounsaturated fatty acids. However, the importance of the minor
52 components, such as phenolic compounds, is becoming more and more noticeable [3-5].
53 This is not surprising as phenols are essential for olive oil resistance to oxidation
54 processes [6,7]. Additionally, the level of these substances is a very important parameter
55 of VOO quality and it largely defines its organoleptic characteristic (flavour,
56 astringency, pungency and bitterness) [8-10]. The phenolic compounds of VOO belong
57 to several classes, such as phenolic acids, phenolic alcohols, flavonoids, hydroxy-
58 isocromans, secoiridoids and lignans [11]. The several factors influence the differences
59 in phenolic compounds composition from one VOO to another: variety of the olive
60 fruit, agricultural techniques used to cultivate the olive fruit, maturity of the olive fruit
61 at harvest time, olive oil extraction, processing, storage methods, etc. [1,11,12,13].
62 Consequently, the phenolic content can be a unique characteristic of olive oil and a
63 very important parameter for quality monitoring.

64 Thus, the structural and quantitative analysis of the individual phenolic compounds
65 present in VOO is an important part in the quality assessment. An analysis of the
66 literature shows HPLC, (used with UV, fluorescence, electrochemical, biosensors, NMR
67 and MS detectors) takes as much as 80% of all described applications of determination
68 of polyphenols in olive oil; gas chromatography (GC) covers another 15% and the rest
69 is covered by such applications as capillary electrophoresis, for example (CE) [11,14-
70 19]. GC was so far was used with FID or MS. So, according to the literature GC is far
71 from being a mainstream method of analyzing of VOO's phenolic compounds.
72 Nevertheless, the results obtained using GC are quite interesting, but the use of GC is
73 less common due to the necessary derivatization and the use of high temperature which
74 could damage the analytes.

75 The first GC analysis of phenolic compounds in olive oil has been reported more than
76 30 years ago [20] by Janer del Valle. This report was soon followed by a study where
77 GC was used for authentication purposes, namely for identification of VOOs and
78 refined oils [21,22]. In 1987, Forcadell et al. [23] developed a protocol for the

79 preparation of trimethylsilyl (TMS) derivatives and Solinas [24] showed the feasibility
80 of this approach for qualitative/quantitative analysis of the phenolic compounds in VOO
81 of several cultivars at different ripening degrees. With the development of analytical
82 instrumentation and mass spectrometers in particular, the methods of compound
83 identification have improved significantly [25-28]. One of the most recent applications
84 was developed by Ríos et al. [14], when they optimized a solid phase extraction-GC-Ion
85 Trap MS method for the qualitative evaluation of phenols in VOO and the structural
86 confirmation of oleuropein and ligstroside aglycons and their oxidation products.
87 The current work is a further attempt to show the feasibility of GC-MS for the analysis
88 of phenolic compounds. However, instead of “classical” GC-MS systems with vacuum
89 stage ionization sources (electron ionization (EI) and chemical ionization (CI)), we
90 evaluated the use GC-MS with a recently developed atmospheric pressure chemical
91 ionization (APCI) source. GC-APCI-MS was introduced in early seventies by Horning
92 [29] but for variety of (mostly technical) reasons has remained an exotic application.
93 The recent explosive development of mass spectrometry instrumentation has created the
94 prerequisites for a reintroduction of GC-APCI-MS [30,31,32]. The aim of this
95 manuscript is to carry out an analytical evaluation of a GC-APCI-TOF MS platform to
96 show the benefits of soft ionization source for GC in combination with a high-end time
97 of flight mass analyzer for analyzing phenolic compounds from virgin olive oil. To
98 achieve this purpose we have performed a complete validation of the developed method
99 regarding its linearity, sensitivity, precision, accuracy and possible matrix effects. We
100 demonstrate that GC-APCI-TOF MS could be used not only for screening of samples,
101 but also for detailed structural analysis and quantitative determination of phenolic
102 compounds. Providing a complementary information to the data obtained by LC-MS,
103 CE-MS or/and other GC-MS configurations, this novel platform may contribute
104 significantly to the development of food analysis and food metabolomics fields.

105

106 **2. Materials and Methods**

107

108 *2.1. Chemicals and samples*

109

110 Only analytical reagent grade chemicals were used for this study. Sinapinic acid,
111 gentisic acid, 4-hydroxyphenylacetic acid, vanillin, vanillic acid, caffeic acid, gallic
112 acid, *trans*-cinnamic acid, protocatechuic acid, *p*-coumaric acid and hydroxytyrosol

113 (HYTY) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA); syringic acid, *m*-
114 coumaric acid, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, homovanillic acid, ferulic acid, taxifolin and
115 tyrosol (TY) were from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland); luteolin (Lut) and apigenin (Apig)
116 were from Extrasynthèse (Genay, France); and pinoresinol (Pin) was purchased from
117 Arbo Nova (Turku, Finland). Dopac was purchased from Fluka and was used as internal
118 standard (IS). Secoiridoids are not available as commercial standards, so we isolated
119 them by semi-preparative HPLC (see section 2.3).

120 The organic solvents, acetonitrile, methanol, and *n*-hexane, were from Sigma Aldrich
121 (St. Louis, MO, USA) and acetic acid from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Deionized
122 and organic-eliminated water was from the water purifier system (USF^{ELGA} from
123 Purelab Plus, Ransbach-Baumbach, Germany).

124 *N,O*-bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide with 1% trimethylchlorosilane (BSTFA +
125 1% TMCS) and *N*-methyl-*N*-trimethylsilyltrifluoroacetamide with 1%
126 trimethylchlorosilane (MSTFA + 1% TMCS) from Pierce (Oud-Beyerland, The
127 Netherlands) were used as derivatization reagents. These reagents were used from
128 freshly opened 1 ml bottles. Methoxyamine hydrochloride was purchased from Supelco.

129

130 Spanish extra-VOO samples used in the preliminary studies were obtained from unique
131 varieties of olive fruit named Picual, Arbequina, Cornicabra, Frantoio and Hojiblanca
132 (January 2009). A mixture of two varieties Picual/Arbequina (50/50, v/v) was used as
133 analytical quality control (QC) sample and for the isolation of the different phenolic
134 fractions. The high content of phenols was reason for the selection of these two varieties
135 as QC and source for isolation of phenolic fractions. For validation purposes we used
136 the mentioned above QC samples and a standard mixture composed by eight phenolic
137 compounds (TY, HYTY, homovanillic acid, *p*-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, Lut, Apig
138 and Pin).

139

140 2.2. *Solid phase extraction Procedure*

141

142 The isolation of the phenolic fractions from extra-VOO with Diol-cartridges was
143 performed according to the solid phase extraction (SPE) protocol developed by Gómez-
144 Caravaca et al. [33]. Briefly, the Diol cartridge (1 g / 6 ml, from Supelco) was placed in
145 a vacuum elution apparatus and pre-conditioned by passing 10 ml of methanol and
146 subsequently 10 ml of hexane. About 60 g of extra-VOO was thoroughly mixed with 60

147 ml of hexane and carefully loaded onto the pre-conditioned column, leaving the sample
148 on the solid phase. After a wash with *n*-hexane (15 ml) to remove the non-polar fraction
149 of the oil, the sample was eluted with methanol (40 ml). The eluents were evaporated to
150 dryness under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator at 35°C. The dried residue was
151 then redissolved in 2 ml of methanol.

152

153 *2.3. HPLC isolation of phenolic compounds*

154

155 Compounds of lignans and secoiridoids families are neither available as commercial
156 standards nor can be synthesized easily. Therefore they were isolated from extra-VOO
157 samples by semi-preparative scale chromatography. The isolation of the compounds
158 was carried out from the Diol-SPE extracts of the mixture of extra-VOO
159 (Picual/Arbequina) obtained as described in section 2.2 redissolved in 500 µl of
160 methanol. Two hundred µl of the sample were injected onto the column in order to
161 obtain concentrated profiles with good resolution.

162 Analyses were carried out at room temperature on a System Gold HPLC (Beckman
163 Coulter, Fullerton, CA, USA), including a 126 solvent module, a 168 diode array
164 detector module and a manual sample valve injector with a 500 µl loop (Rheodyne,
165 Cotati, CA, USA). The semi-preparative HPLC C18 column (Phenomenex Gemini, 25
166 cm x 10 mm, 5 µm average particle size) was used at a flow rate of 3 ml/min. The
167 mobile phases consisted of water with 0.5% acetic acid (phase A) and acetonitrile
168 (phase B). The solvent gradient was programmed as following: from 0 to 30 min,
169 95%(A):5%(B) to 80%(A):20%(B); from 30 to 40 min, 80% (A):20% (B) to 70%
170 (A):30% (B); from 40 to 50 min, 70% (A):30% (B) to 65% (A):35% (B); from 50 to 60
171 min, 65% (A):35% (B) to 50% (A):50% (B); from 60 to 70 min, 50%(A):50%(B) to
172 5%(A):95%(B); from 70 to 75 min, 5% (A):95% (B) to 95% (A):5% (B). This last value
173 was maintained for 5 min until the end of a run.

174

175 *2.4. Derivatization reaction*

176

177 The derivatization reaction was carried out by adding 50 µL of BSTFA plus 1% TMCS
178 to the dried sample. The solution was vortexed for 1 min and the trimethylsilylation
179 reaction was performed at room temperature for 30 min. A minimum of 30 min

180 equilibration time was used before the sample injection. The stability of BSTFA-
181 derivatized samples, kept at ambient temperature (20-25°C), was determined
182 periodically by injecting replicate preparations of the processed samples consecutively
183 for up to 48 h. Peak areas were chosen as parameter for stability evaluation.

184 A nitrogen flow was used for drying the standard mixture, the extra-VOO extracts and
185 the isolated fractions to complete dryness. Then, the derivatization reagent was added.

186

187 *2.5. GC-APCI-MaXis MS optima conditions*

188

189 The GC experiments were performed using an Agilent 7890A GC (Agilent, Palo Alto,
190 USA) equipped with a HP-5-MS column (30 m, 0.25 mm ID, 0.25 µm film thickness).

191 An aliquot of the derivatized samples (1 µl) was applied by splitless injection (injection
192 time 60 s) with a programmable CTC PAL multipurpose-sampler (CTC Analytics AG,
193 Zwingen, Switzerland). Injection programs included sequential washing steps of the 10
194 µl syringe before and after the injection, and a sample pumping step for removal of
195 small air bubbles. Helium was used as carrier gas and the injector temperature was set
196 250°C.

197 Two temperature gradients were used during the study. Gradient one (run 1) was
198 applied for the exploratory experiments: the column temperature was initially kept at
199 170°C for 5 min, then from 170 to 255°C at 3°C/min, keeping that value for 1 min and
200 finally from 255 to 310°C at 2° C/min and maintaining that temperature for 10 min. A
201 constant flow rate of 0.5 ml/min was used. Using the described chromatographic
202 conditions, the analysis time was about 70 min. Gradient two (run 2) of 50 minutes was
203 used consequently for more routine measurements: the column temperature was initially
204 kept at 160°C for 5 min, from 160 to 188°C at 3° C/min keeping that value for 1 min,
205 from 188 to 241 at 15°C/min, keeping that value for 1 min, from 241 to 282°C at
206 2°C/min, from 282°C to 310°C at 5°C/min and maintaining that temperature for 5 min.
207 A constant flow rate of 1.0 ml/min was used.

208

209 The GC system was coupled to an ultra high resolution time of flight mass spectrometer
210 maXis (UHR TOF MS, maXis, Bruker Daltonik, Bremen, Germany) using a
211 multipurpose source equipped with GC transfer line [31]. The parameters of the APCI
212 interface and all the parameters of the maXis MS detector were optimized using the area
213 of the MS signal for the polyphenols. The GC transfer line to the mass spectrometer was

214 kept at 300°C. The APCI source and MS were operated in positive mode. The pressure
215 of the nebulizer gas (nitrogen) was set to 2 bars and temperature and flow rate of the dry
216 gas (nitrogen) were 250°C and 5.00 l/min, respectively. The APCI vaporizer
217 temperature was 450°C and the voltage of the corona discharge needle was 2000 nA.
218 The mass analyzer was operating a mass range from 50 to 1000 at spectra rate of 1 Hz.
219 With these conditions a resolving power up to 45000 was obtained. The instrument was
220 calibrated externally using an APCI calibration tune mix. In addition, an internal
221 calibration using cyclic-siloxanes (a typical background in GC-MS [34]) was used. The
222 SmartFormula™ tool of DataAnalysis package (Bruker Daltonik, Bremen, Germany)
223 was used for the calculation of elemental composition of compounds.

224

225 Two different MS/MS modes were used in the study: auto-MS/MS and multiple
226 reaction monitoring (MRM). In the auto MS/MS mode, the spectra were produced by
227 fragmentation of the main detected ions under general collision conditions for all of
228 them. In the MRM mode, the appropriate precursor ion for every compound was
229 selected and fragmented according to its own parameters (collision energy, isolation
230 width, ISCID energy, amplitude). Besides, as the number of compounds studied was
231 quite high and some masses were present throughout the entire chromatogram, we
232 created several segments in our MS method, and in each one we chose the appropriate
233 precursor ions with their own isolation and fragmentation conditions. The MS/MS
234 spectra were acquired in eight different elution time windows: 0-9.1, 9.1-20, 20-40.8,
235 40.8-46.0, 46.0-52.0, 51.0-56.0, 56.0-62.2, and from 62.2 to the end of the run (elution
236 time windows for run 1). Nitrogen was used as collision gas and the collision energy
237 was set from 15 to 35 eV.

238

239 *2.6. Validation experiments using extra-VOO quality control (QC) samples*

240

241 *2.6.1. Specificity*

242

243 The specificity of the method was tested by screening analysis of phenolic-free oil
244 samples or blank samples (refined sunflower oil). Refined sunflower oil was only used
245 to evaluate the specificity of our method.

246

247 *2.6.2. Linearity and sensitivity*

248

249 The linearity of the detector response was verified with standard solutions at ten
250 different concentration levels over the range from the quantification limit to 250 ppm.
251 Each point of the calibration graph corresponded to the mean value from three
252 independent replicate injections. Calibration curves were obtained for each standard by
253 plotting the standard concentration as a function of the peak area obtained from GC-
254 APCI-MaXis MS analyses. The sensitivity of the analytical procedure was calculated by
255 defining the limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) for the individual
256 analytes included in standard solutions according to the IUPAC method [35]. The
257 lowest concentration that could be detected with a reasonable certainty for our analytical
258 procedure (LOD) was considered $S/N = 3$, whilst LOQ was $S/N = 10$.

259

260 *2.6.3. Precision and accuracy*

261

262 The precision of the analytical procedure described was measured as repeatability and
263 evaluated over the linear dynamic range at three different concentration levels (low
264 (LOQ), medium (intermediate concentration value of the linear calibration range), high
265 (higher concentration value of the linear calibration range)). Spiked quality control (QC)
266 samples were tested in six replicates per concentration and calculated with calibration
267 curves obtained daily. The precision of the analytical procedure was expressed as the
268 relative standard deviation (RSD). The intra- and inter-day repeatability in the peak
269 areas was determined as the RSD obtained for six consecutive injections of each phenol
270 at each concentration value, carried out within the same day and on three different days.
271 Accuracy was evaluated with separately prepared individual primary stock solutions,
272 mixtures and working solutions of all standards. It was calculated over the linear
273 dynamic range at three different concentration levels, i.e. (low (LOQ), medium
274 (intermediate concentration value of the linear calibration range), high (higher
275 concentration value of the linear calibration range)) by three determinations per
276 concentration on different days. The analyte concentrations were calculated from daily
277 calibration curves and the accuracy was calculated by the ratio of this calculated
278 concentration versus the theoretical (spiked) concentration.

279

280 *2.6.4. Matrix effects*

281

282 To evaluate the matrix effect, we compared the MS response of the analytes under study
283 spiked post-extraction with those in a pure solvent solution (in triplicate), calculating
284 the response factors (RF, which is considered to be the ratio between the peak area and
285 the concentration of the analyte) when the analytes were in presence of the olive oil
286 matrix and in a neat solution. We checked whether significant differences between both
287 values could be found using ANOVA.

288

289 **3. Results and Discussion**

290

291 *3.1. GC-APCI-MaXis MS analysis. Preliminary studies*

292

293 The effects of several parameters such as the concentration of derivatization reagent,
294 reaction time and temperature were studied. We have achieved the best performance
295 adding 50 μ L of BSTFA + 1% TMCS to the dried sample at room temperature and
296 incubation time 1 hour. The effect of including an intermediate step of
297 methoxyamination was adequately evaluated and no change in the peak area or stability
298 was observed.

299 Further, we have optimized the chromatographic and MS (APCI and MaXis) conditions
300 for the maximum coverage, resolution and sensitivity, using the phenolic extracts from
301 extra-VOO. Several varieties of olive oil (Picual, Arbequina, Cornicabra, Frantoio and
302 Hojiblanca) were used during the optimization to ensure the applicability of the
303 presented methodology for the analysis of these compounds in any kind of olive oil. The
304 effect of different GC parameters (gas flow, sample injection and temperature gradient)
305 and mass spectrometry conditions (position of the column in the transfer line, transfer
306 line temperature, flow rate and pressure of nebulizer gas, vaporizer temperature,
307 voltages in the corona and other source and ion transfer settings) were studied, and
308 finally the conditions described in material and methods as run 1 were chosen as
309 optimum. [Fig. 1](#) shows the Base Peak Chromatogram (BPC) of an olive oil extract
310 (mixture Picual/Arbequina) achieved by using the optimum GC-APCI-MaXis MS
311 procedure described above. Using these conditions, the analysis time was about 70 min
312 and a clean chromatogram was obtained with high efficiency and good separation of a
313 great number of compounds.

314

315 *3.2. Identification of the compounds*

316

317 For the peaks assignment a combination of prior knowledge, commercially available
318 analytical standards and semi-preparative HPLC isolated fractions was used. In
319 addition, MS/MS experiments were carried out to confirm the identification of the
320 compounds.

321

322 *3.2.1. GC-APCI-MaXis MS analysis of standard mixture*

323

324 A standard mixture consisting of 22 commercially available phenolic compounds was
325 analyzed under the optimal conditions to understand the signal that each phenolic
326 compound produced in the system APCI-MaXis MS. They have been only studied so
327 far by the classical ionization techniques coupled to GC, mainly with electron ionization
328 which is a rather harsh technique. [Table 1](#) summarizes data for all components of the
329 mixture including their molecular formula, retention time, measured and theoretical m/z ,
330 relative abundance of each m/z signal present in the MS spectra, error (mDa) and
331 mSigma value. The mass position error remained within 2.1 mDa and high quality
332 Sigma fit values (< 20 mSigma) were obtained for all compounds. We have highlighted
333 in bold the prevalent ion which was observed in the MS spectrum.

334 All the compounds showed the complete silylation of their active hydrogen although
335 they show different “resistance” to the in-source fragmentation process. For example, in
336 such compounds as the flavonoids Lut and Apig, vanillin and phenolic acids with an
337 acidic group in para-position to hydroxyl group (protocatechuic acid, syringic acid and
338 gallic acid), the parent ion remains the most intense ion in the spectra. For other
339 phenolic acids and compounds such as Pin (a lignan) and TY and HYTY (simple
340 phenols), the products of in-source fragmentation appeared to be the most intense ions
341 in the spectra. Simple phenols like TY and HYTY are represented by the radical $[M-$
342 $XH+XTMS]^{\bullet+}$ instead of the molecular ion $[M-XH+XTMS+H]^+$. In general, all the
343 phenolic compounds showed the same losses of 16 and 90, which might correspond to
344 the fragments CH_4 and C_3H_9SiO (trimethylsilyl group with an oxygen), respectively.
345 This last loss (90) yields the prevalent ion in the spectrum of majority of the
346 compounds. In the case of simple phenols a loss of 89 was observed, probably due to
347 the presence of the radicals, as mentioned above. For the phenolic acids such as 4-
348 hydroxyphenylacetic acid, homovanillic acid and dopac, with an acetic acid in their
349 structure, the prevalent ion corresponded to the loss of 118 ($72 (-C_3H_9Si)$ plus 46,

350 which corresponds to $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{OH}+\text{CO}$). The flavonoids, Lut and Apig, undergo low
351 fragmentation with a main loss of 72 which corresponds to the trimethylsilyl group (-
352 $\text{C}_3\text{H}_9\text{Si}$), and Pin showed the fragment 485 corresponding to a loss of 18. Thus, in-
353 source fragmentation observed practically for all tested standards may have a negative
354 effect reducing the intensity of the parent ions but, the fragmentation patterns appear to
355 be compound specific and as such can be efficiently used for the structure confirmation.

356

357 *3.2.2. Analysis of the isolated phenolic fractions*

358

359 There are no commercial standards available for all phenolic compounds of extra-VOO.
360 Consequently, a semi-preparative HPLC (see experimental section 2.3) was used for the
361 isolation of such important compounds as secoiridoids (oleuropein aglycon (Ol Agl),
362 ligitroside aglycon (Lig Agl) and their derivatives) and some lignans ((+)-1-
363 acetoxypinoresinol (Ac Pin) and syringaresinol). In total, nine different fractions were
364 isolated. To obtain reference APCI-MS spectrum for the compounds present in every
365 HPLC isolated fraction, the 9 phenolic fractions were analyzed individually with GC-
366 APCI-TOF MS. Fig. 2 shows the BPC of the phenolic extract from an extra-VOO
367 sample and the 9 isolated fractions (in colour) analyzed by using the developed GC
368 method (run 1). A semi-preparative purification provides no 100% pure compounds,
369 therefore a number of peaks were observed in BPCs of each individual fraction. The
370 combination of prior knowledge [36], the superior mass accuracy of TOF mass analyzer
371 and isotopic distribution (SigmaFit) was used for structural assignment of the
372 compounds. Table 2 summarizes the information about each isolated fraction, including
373 the main phenolic compounds identified in each fraction with their retention time,
374 experimental m/z , molecular formula, mass error and SigmaFit quality value. In-source
375 fragmentation of the parent ions was clearly observed and, in several cases, the
376 fragmentation patterns played an important part in the compound identification. In the
377 mentioned table, we have included some information about the relative intensity of the
378 m/z signals present in the MS spectra of the phenols. In fraction 1, elenolic acid (EA)
379 and different isomers were identified with the fragments corresponding to a mass loss of
380 32 and 90. The compound corresponding to the silylation of two active hydrogens (m/z
381 387) might correspond to the presence of another isomeric form of EA. Lignans Ac Pin
382 and syringaresinol were identified in fractions 5th and 6th respectively, and in both cases
383 the loss of 18, 89 and 256, as in the case of Pin, was observed. The main secoiridoids

384 (Ol Agl and Lig Agl), their isomers and related compounds (decarboxilated derivatives
385 of Ol Agl (DOA), decarboxilated derivatives of Lig Agl (D-Lig Agl), 10-hydroxy-
386 oleuropein aglycon (10-H Ol Agl)) were identified as well. In general, for the Ol Agl
387 and their derivatives, we observed with a high intensity the fragment 281, and for Lig
388 Agl and derivatives the fragment 193. Besides, in most of the compounds a mass loss of
389 32 and 90 (C₃H₉SiO) was observed. Different silylated forms were found for Ol Agl
390 (Ol Agl-2H+2TMS and Ol Agl-3H+3TMS) and Lig Agl (Lig Agl-H+TMS and Lig Agl-
391 2H+2TMS) probably due to the presence of different isomeric forms (aldehydic or
392 dialdehydic form of EA).

393

394 3.2.3. MS/MS analyses

395

396 Assignment of phenolic compounds using reference spectra and prior knowledge is a
397 practical tool for the screening of new products and testing quality of olive oil mixtures.
398 However, unequivocal *de novo* identification of new compounds demands analysis of
399 MS/MS spectra. Two different MS/MS modes were used in the study: auto-MS/MS and
400 MRM. Every peak detected in the profile was isolated and further fragmented after
401 applying the required energy to get a clean MS/MS spectrum. When a compound yields
402 more than one *m/z* value, we considered as precursor ions all the different *m/z* signals
403 observed in the MS spectrum for making MS/MS analyses. Table 3 includes the *m/z*
404 APCI-MaXis MS/MS signals detected for the most relevant phenolic compounds
405 present in the extract of extra-virgin olive oil. The prevalent ion in the MS spectrum for
406 each compound is highlighted in bold. In this way, we were able to unequivocally
407 identify several of phenolic compounds in the GC-APCI-MaXis MS of an extra-VOO.
408 MS/MS analysis proved to be especially useful for confirmation of the structures of
409 secoiridoids derivatives such as Lig Agl and Ol Agl. In total, we found eight ligstroside
410 derivatives and eleven oleuropein derivatives. Indeed, the intact secoiridoids, such as
411 oleuropein glucoside and ligstroside glucoside, are undetectable in olive oil; due to the
412 high solubility in water they are depleted during olive storage and olive oil extraction.
413 Moreover, they undergo enzymatic hydrolysis first producing Ol Agl and Lig Agl upon
414 removal of the attached glucose moiety and then a number of secoiridoid derivatives
415 upon further molecular transformations via ring opening and rearranged re-closure [37].
416 Thus, enzymatic hydrolysis may explain the presence of the many isomeric or related
417 forms in this family of compounds and the complexity of the secoiridoids group [38].

418 When the MS/MS behaviour of compounds such as TY is analyzed, we observe a
419 fragment 109 m/z of the precursor ion 193 m/z . The same effect is observed for TY
420 analogues (Lig Agl, for example), with a fragment 109 as prevalent ion in the MS/MS
421 spectra. If we study the fragmentation pattern from HYTY analogues (DOA, Methyl Ol
422 Agl, hydroxy-decarboxilated-oleuropein aglycon (H-D-Ol Agl), 10-hydroxy-Ol Agl),
423 we observe that the main fragment of 193 m/z comes from a precursor of 281 m/z . For
424 Ol Agl-related compounds a 118 m/z fragment would appear to be specific. Keeping
425 that in mind, we might suggest that the fragmentation pattern may reveal whether a
426 compound is a derivative of TY or of HYTY.

427 Flavonoids demonstrate weak fragmentation and, in general, require higher
428 fragmentation energies. For both flavonoids under study (Apig and Lut), the loss of 16
429 (CH₄) yields the prevalent ion in the MS/MS spectrum.

430 Lignans, such as Ac Pin and Pin showed in their MS/MS spectra the fragment 209,
431 which is attributable to the stable substituted tropylium ion structure. This ion shows up
432 in the MS/MS spectrum from lignans containing two methoxytrimethylsilyl ether
433 benzylic moieties with either the C-7 or C-7' containing one or two hydrogens. The ion
434 m/z 209 can shift to 239 (as in the case of syringaresinol) with the addition of a second
435 methoxy group to the aromatic rings.

436

437 In conclusion, the combination of analytical standards, MS and MS/MS analysis of
438 semi-preparative fractions and the prior knowledge gives us the possibility to perform a
439 detailed assignment of phenolic compounds in our test sample (a mixture of Arbequina
440 and Picual oils). Fig. 1 showed the BPC of the Diol-SPE extract obtained from a
441 mixture of Arbequina and Picual oils; the approach used for the assignment of a
442 particular structure is colour coded: commercial standards - blue, phenolic fractions -
443 red and prior knowledge - purple. Analysis of the chromatogram reveals a clear pattern
444 of the migration for the phenolic compounds of different families: simple phenols and
445 phenolic acids reappear first, followed by secoiridoids, flavonoids and lignans.

446 After achieving the identification of 28 compounds in the profile and define the elution
447 areas of each family of phenols, we re-optimized the GC method in terms of flow rate
448 and temperature gradient in order to improve chromatographic resolution in the “areas
449 of interest” and to reduce the total analysis time. The method described in Materials and
450 Methods as “run 2” was used for further experiments. The total analysis time with the
451 modified conditions was reduced to 50 minutes, while maintaining good resolution and

452 efficiency. To carry out the validation of our method and for the application of the
453 method to the analysis of different extra-VOOs, we used run 2.

454

455 3.3. Validation experiments. Analytical parameters of the method

456

457 The stability of derivatized samples is an important factor for large scale food
458 metabolomics studies. To address this issue, we kept derivatized samples in 1.5 ml
459 screw capped vials (with inserted micro-vials) at room temperature and performed
460 analysis at equal time intervals between 0 and 48 h. Data proved to be rather consistent
461 from 0 to 35 h. However, data collected at later time points demonstrated a steadily
462 increasing variability. Thus, if a technical solution of the derivatization problem, such as
463 for example, on-line sample processing is not available, material should be processed
464 within the first 24 hours to avoid any possible risk of derivatization-dependent
465 variability.

466 The specificity of the developed method was tested by analysis of blank oil samples or
467 phenolic-free oil samples (refined sunflower oil) and no significant chromatographic
468 interference around the retention times of the analytes was observed.

469 Calibration curves were obtained for each standard by plotting the peak areas as a
470 function of the concentration. The parameters of the calibration functions: LOD, LOQ,
471 linearity, calibration range, correlation coefficient, repeatability and accuracy have been
472 summarized in [Table 4](#). Several factors have influenced the selection of compounds for
473 the calculation of the calibration curves and validation experiments: a) availability of
474 the analytical standards; b) the presence of a given compound in extra-VOO samples
475 and c) an attempt to keep the selection as diverse as possible. Those standards of
476 phenolic compounds used in the preliminary studies which were not present in the
477 analyzed samples of extra-VOOs were not included in the final selection of analytes,
478 which includes: TY, HYTY, homovanillic acid, *p*-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, Lut,
479 Apig, and Pin. In order to calculate the calibration functions and LOD's we took the
480 EIC of the most intense ion in the mass spectrum for each selected compound. If the
481 compound was represented by more than one silylated form, the one with higher
482 linearity in the calibration range was used for calculation of analytical parameters. For
483 example, in the case of tyrosol, for quantitation we used the *m/z* signal 193.1061; for
484 homovanillic acid, we used *m/z* 209.1007; for *p*-coumaric, we used *m/z* 309.1333; for
485 ferulic acid, *m/z* 249.0967; for luteolin, *m/z* 575.2142; for apigenin, we used *m/z*

486 487.1792; and for pinoresinol - m/z 485.2189. All calibration curves showed good
487 linearity ($r^2 > 0.985$) for the selected concentration range. LODs were found to be within
488 the range between 0.13 and 1.05 ppm, for Pin and Lut, respectively. The intra- and
489 inter-day repeatability in the peak areas was determined as the RSD obtained for six
490 consecutive injections of the analytical QC sample spiked with each phenol at an
491 intermediate concentration value of the calibration curve, carried out within the same
492 day and on three different days. Acceptable levels of precision were obtained for the
493 developed method in terms of repeatability since in all cases RSDs calculated were
494 lower than 6.07%. The accuracy ranged from 95.4% to 101.5%.

495 As described above, to evaluate the matrix effect, RFs of the 8 phenols when the
496 analytes were in presence of the olive oil matrix and in a neat solution were determined.
497 No statistical differences in peak area and response factors were observed for any of the
498 analytes under study.

499

500 *3.4. Application of the method to the analysis of different extra-VOOs*

501

502 Finally, to demonstrate the feasibility of our method for analysis of real samples we
503 have analyzed the extracts of three different commercial extra-VOOs: a) a mixture of
504 Arbequina and Picual, b) Frantoio, and c) Hojiblanca. All samples were analyzed in
505 triplicate ($n = 3$). The representative chromatograms are shown [Fig. 3a](#). To facilitate
506 visual comparison, the intensity scale was kept the same in all cases. Already visual
507 inspection of BPCs shows significant differences between the samples. The quantitative
508 data summarized in [Table 5](#) provide a numeric expression of the differences found for
509 the different products. Since standards for complex phenols and elenolic acid are not
510 available, in the table we included their quantification in terms of other commercial
511 standards (TY and HYTY, respectively). Using TY and HYTY for the quantification of
512 ligstroside- or oleuropein-analogues is quite common, since those compounds contain
513 TY and HYTY in their structure.

514 Our results show that Frantoio extra-VOO has the lowest phenolic content; it has the
515 lowest concentration of simple phenols (tyrosol and hydroxytyrosol) and secoiridoids.
516 The content of flavonoids, on the contrary, is comparable with Hojiblanca extra-VOO.
517 As far as Ac Pin content is concerned, Frantoio is the richest oil.

518 Levels of simple phenols found in Hojiblanca extra-VOO appeared to be higher than in
519 the other two samples. The mix of Picual and Arbequina, however, shows a high

520 content of secoiridoids (Ol Agl, Lig Agl and their derivatives). The levels of
521 decarboxylated forms of Ol Agl and Lig Agl (DOA and D-Lig Agl) in Picual-Arbequina
522 mix were found to be 12.76 and 6.55 mg/kg, respectively, whilst in the other samples
523 they were present at much lower concentrations. The comparison of Ol Agl (35.3 min)
524 concentrations revealed even stronger differences between the samples: 46.04 mg/kg for
525 Picual-Arbequina, 2.27 mg/kg for Hojiblanca and below detection limits for Frantoio. A
526 similar trend was observed for another isomer of Ol Agl (38.3 min). In general, the
527 content of Ol Agl- and Lig Agl-derivatives in olive oils could be estimated quickly from
528 APCI-GC data using EICs, 281.2481, and 193.1944, respectively. Fig. 3b shows an
529 example of such analysis, which appears to be useful in the future for making a quick
530 estimation of oleuropein- and ligstroside-analogues amount.

531

532 **4. Conclusions**

533

534 Here, we demonstrate for the first time the applicability of Gas Chromatography with
535 Atmospheric Pressure Ionization source (GC-APCI-MaXis-MS) for the qualitative and
536 quantitative analysis of the phenolic compounds present in extra-VOO samples. A
537 combination of prior knowledge, commercially available standards and semi-
538 preparative HPLC isolated standards, supported by intrinsic qualities of the UHR-TOF
539 mass analyzer (operating in MS, auto-MS/MS and MRM modes), gave us the
540 opportunity to perform detailed analysis of phenolic profiles of the extra-VOOs.
541 Moreover, a complete validation of the method was carried out considering the
542 specificity, linearity, sensitivity, precision, accuracy and matrix effects. Thus, GC with
543 the soft atmospheric pressure ionization source and UHR-TOF mass analyzer may offer
544 new complementary information in addition the methods used widely so far to analyze
545 dietary phenolic compounds.

546

547 **Acknowledgments**

548 The authors are very grateful to Ministry of Education and Science (Project AGL 2008-
549 05108-C03-03/ALI), and Junta de Andalucía (Project P07-AGR-02619 and Project P09-
550 FQM-5469).

551

552

553 **Caption to figures**

554

555 **Fig 1.** Base Peak Chromatogram (BPC) of the Diol-SPE extract of a mixture of
556 Arbequina and Picual oils.

557 Elution windows of different phenolic fraction of EVOO are shown. The peaks have been identified by
558 standards (blue), isolated fractions (red), prior knowledge (literature) (purple). The peaks with
559 considerable intensity which have not been identified are marked in green.

560 **Peak identification:** 1, Ty-2H+2TMS, 2, Isolated 4, 3, *m/z* 281.0966/192.9388, 4, Hyty-3H+3TMS, 5,
561 Protocatechuic acid-3H+3TMS+H, 6, Dopac-3H+3TMS+H, 7, EA-1H+1TMS+H, 8, EA-
562 1H+1TMS+H/Isolated 2, 9, Isolated 6 (D-Lig Agl), 10, Isolated 6, 11, Isolated 6, 12, DOA-
563 2H+2TMS+H, 13, *m/z* 501.3843/411.3312, 14, Lig Agl-1H+1TMS+H, 15, Methyl Ol Agl-2H+2TMS+H,
564 16, H-D-Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H, 17, Isolated 6 (Lig Agl), 18, Isolated 6 (Lig Agl), 19, Ol Agl-
565 2H+2TMS+H, 20, Isolated 8, 21, 10 H-Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H, 22, Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H, 23, Apigenin-
566 3H+3TMS+H, 24, Luteolin-4H+4TMS+H, 25, Pinoresinol-2H+2TMS+H, 26, *m/z* 397.3825, 27,
567 Acetoxy-pinoresinol-2H+2TMS+H, 28, Syringaresinol-2H+2TMS+H.

568

569 **Fig. 2.** (BPCs) of the phenolic extract from an extra-VOO sample and the 9 isolated
570 fractions (in colour) analyzed by using GC run 1.

571 The peak with retention time 36.7 min present in every fraction has not been considered
572 since it belongs to BSTFA derivatization reagent.

573

574 **Fig. 3.** Polyphenolic profiles (BPCs) of the three extra-VOOs (run 2).

575 A) a mixture of Arbequina and Picual extra-VOOs, Frantoio extra-VOO and Hojiblanca
576 extra-VOO Auchan.

577 B) Extracted Ion Chromatograms (EICs) of *m/z* 281.2480 and 193.1944, which facilitate the
578 study of the Ol Agl-derivatives and Lig Agl-derivatives or related compounds.

579 **Peak identification:** 1, Ty-2H+2TMS; 2, Hyty-3H+3TMS; 3, Protocatechuic acid-3H+3TMS+H; 4,
580 Dopac-3H+3TMS+H; 5, EA-1H+1TMS+H; 6, D-Lig Agl; 7, compound present in isolated fraction 6 (Lig
581 Agl-related comp); 8, compound present in isolated fraction 6 (Lig Agl-related comp); 9, DOA-
582 2H+2TMS+H; 10, *m/z* 501.3843/411.3312; 11, Lig Agl-1H+1TMS+H; 12, Methyl Ol Agl-2H+2TMS+H;
583 13, H-D-Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H; 14, Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H; 15, Ol Agl-2H+2TMS+H; 16, Ol Agl-
584 3H+3TMS+H and related comp; 17, Apigenin-3H+3TMS+H; 18, Luteolin-4H+4TMS+H; 19,
585 Pinoresinol-2H+2TMS+H; 20, 397.3825; 21, Acetoxy-pinoresinol-2H+2TMS+H.

586

587

-
- [1] S. Cicerale, X.A. Conlan, A.J. Sinclair, R.S.J. Keast, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 49 (2009) 218.
- [2] C. Fortes, F. Forastiere, S. Farchi, S. Mallone, T. Trequatrinini, F. Anatra, G. Schmid, C.A. Perucci, *Nutrition and Cancer*, 46 (2003) 30.
- [3] E. Tripoli, M. Giammanco, G. Tabacchi, D. Di Majo, S. Giammanco, M. La Guardia, *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 18 (2005) 98.
- [4] J.A. Menéndez, A. Vázquez-Martin, C. Oliveras-Ferraros, R. García-Villalba, A. Carrasco-Pancorbo, A. Fernández-Gutiérrez, A. Segura-Carretero, *Int. J. Oncol.* 34 (2009) 43.
- [5] R.W. Owen, A. Giacosa, W.E. Hull, R. Haubner, B. Spiegelhalder, H. Bartsch, *Eur. J. Cancer* 36 (2000) 1235.
- [6] R. Briante, F. Febbraio, R. Nucci, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 51 (2003) 6975.
- [7] J. Velasco, C. Dobarganes, *Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol.* 104 (2002) 661.
- [8] F. Gutiérrez-Rosales, J.J. Ríos, M.L. Gómez-Rey, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 51 (2003) 6021.
- [9] S. Siliani A. Mattei, L.B. Innocenti, B. Zanoni, *J. Food Qual.* 29 (2006) 431.
- [10] L. Cerretani, M.D. Salvador, A. Bendini, G. Fregapane, *Chem. Percept.* 1 (2008) 258.
- [11] A. Carrasco-Pancorbo, L. Cerretani, A. Bendini, A. Segura-Carretero, T. Gallina-Toschi, A. Fernández-Gutiérrez, *J. Sep. Sci.* 28 (2005) 837.
- [12] M. Brenes, A. Garcia, P. Garcia, J.J. Rios, A. Garrido, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 47 (1999) 3535.
- [13] A. Gomez-Rico, M.D. Salvador, M. La Greca, G. Fregapane, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 54 (2006) 7130.
- [14] J.J. Ríos, M.J. Gil, F. Gutiérrez-Rosales, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1093 (2005) 167.
- [15] M. Suárez, A. Macia, M. P. Romero, M. J. Motilva, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1214 (2008) 90.
- [16] M.J. Oliveras-Lopez, M. Innocenti, C. Giaccherini, F. Ieri, A. Romani, N. Mulinacci, *Talanta* 73 (2007) 726.
- [17] R. Mateos, M.M. Domínguez, J.L. Espartero, A. Cert, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 51 (2003) 7170.
- [18] A. Carrasco-Pancorbo, A.M. Gómez-Caravaca, L. Cerretani, A. Bendini, A. Segura-Carretero, A. Fernández-Gutiérrez, *J. Sep. Sci.* 29 (2006) 2221.
- [19] A. Carrasco-Pancorbo, C. Neuss, M. Pelzing, A. Segura-Carretero, A. Fernández-Gutiérrez, *Electrophoresis* 28 (2007) 806.
- [20] C. Janer del Valle, A. Vázquez-Roncero, *Grasas Aceites* 5 (1980) 309.
- [21] M. Solinas, A. Cichelli, *Riv. Soc. Ital. Sci. Aliment.* 10 (1981) 159.
- [22] M. Solinas, A. Cichelli, *Riv. Soc. Ital. Sci. Aliment.* 11 (1982) 223.
- [23] M.L. Forcadell, M. Comas, X. Miquel, M.C. de la Torre, *Rev. Fr. Corps Gras.* 34 (1987) 547.
- [24] M. Solinas, *Riv. Ital. Sostanze Grasse* 64 (1987) 255.
- [25] F. Angerosa, N. D'Alessandro, P. Konstantinou, L. Di Giacinto, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 43 (1995) 1802.
- [26] M. Tasioula-Margari, O. Okogeri, *J. Food. Sci.* 66 (2001) 530.
- [27] F. Angerosa, N. D'Alessandro, F. Corana, G. Mellerio, *J. Chromatogr. A* 736 (1996) 195.
- [28] M. Saitta, S. Lo Curto, F. Salvo, G. Di Bella, G. Dugo, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 466 (2002) 335.
- [29] E.C. Horning, M.G. Horning, D.I. Carroll, I. Dzidic, R.N. Stillwell, *Anal. Chem.* 45 (1973) 936.
- [30] C.N. McEwen, R.G. McKay, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 16 (2005) 1730.
- [31] R. Schiewek, M. Lorenz, R. Giese, K. Brockmann, T. Benter, S. Gäb, O.J. Schmitz, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 392 (2008) 87.
- [32] A. Carrasco-Pancorbo, E. Nevedomskaya, T. Arthen-Engeland, T. Zey, G. Zurek, C. Baessmann, A.M. Deelder, O. A. Mayboroda, *Anal. Chem.* 81 (2009) 10071.
- [33] A.M. Gómez-Caravaca, A. Carrasco-Pancorbo, B. Cañabate-Diaz, A. Segura-Carretero, A. Fernández-Gutiérrez, *Electrophoresis* 26 (2005) 3538.
- [34] B.O. Keller, J. Sui, A.B. Young, R.M. Whittal, *Analytica Chimica Acta* 627 (2008) 71.
- [35] L. A. Curie, *Pure Appl. Chem.* 67 (1995) 1699.
- [36] R. García-Villalba, A. Carrasco-Pancorbo, A. Vázquez-Martín, C. Oliveras-Ferraros, J.A. Menéndez, A. Segura-Carretero, A. Fernández-Gutiérrez, *Electrophoresis* 30 (2009) 2688.
- [37] A. Piperno, M. Toscano, N. A. Uccella, *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 84 (2004) 341.
- [38] K. De la Torre-Carbot, O. Jauregui, E. Gimeno, A. I. Castellote, R. M. Lamuela-Raventós, M. C. López-Sabater, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 53 (2005) 4331.

Figure

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Table 1

GC-APCI-TOF MS signals (m/z) of the set of commercially available standards of the phenolic compounds.

The prevalent ion in the MS spectrum for each compound highlighted in bold. The relative intensity of the other m/z signals present in the MS spectra of the phenols is shown between brackets (considering the prevalent ion in bold letter as 100%).

m/z experimental	Retention time (minutes)	Predicted molecular composition	m/z theoretical	Error (mDa)	mSigma Value	In-source fragmentation pattern	Compound identity
225.0939	9.4	C11H17O3Si	225.0941	0.2	7.8	209.0992 (7) / 197.1001 (39) / 166.0457 (21)	Vanillin-1H+1TMS+H
221.0998 (10)	9.7	C12H17O2Si	221.0992	-0.6	4.1	205.0698 (53) / 161.0794 (18) / 131.0507	<i>trans</i> -Cinnamic acid-1H+1TMS+H
282.1470 (5)	10.0	C14H26O2Si2	282.1466	-0.4	5.1	258.0970 (9) / 193.1061	Tyrosol-2H+2TMS
283.1165 (30)	11.3	C13H23O3Si2	283.1180	1.5	5.7	267.0908 (61) / 193.0713	4-Hydroxybenzoic acid-2H+2TMS+H
297.1316 (5)	11.6	C14H25O3Si2	297.1337	2.1	4.5	283.0791 (5) / 267.0379 (12) / 178.9282	4-Hydroxyphenylacetic acid-2H+2TMS+H
313.1287 (46)	14.9	C14H25O4Si2	313.1286	-0.1	3.1	297.1022 (54) / 223.0817	Vanillic acid-2H+2TMS+H
370.1809 (10)	15.1	C17H34O3Si3	370.1810	0.1	10.6	281.1410 / 193.0691 (20)	Hydroxytyrosol-3H+3TMS
327.1426 (5)	15.2	C15H27O4Si2	327.1442	0.1	7.1	281.1401 (20) / 209.1007 / 137.0600 (13)	Homovanillic acid-2H+2TMS+H
371.1563 (39)	15.4	C16H31O4Si3	371.1525	0.2	9.6	355.1248 (10) / 281.1060 / 209.0646 (15)	Genticic acid-3H+3TMS+H
371.1565	16.6	C16H31O4Si3	371.1525	-1.0	15.1	355.1273 (23) / 281.1075 (46)	Protocatechuic acid-3H+3TMS+H
385.1676 (11)	17.0	C17H33O4Si3	385.1681	0.5	9.4	267.0719 / 172.7891 (7)	Dopac-3H+3TMS+H
309.1347 (33)	17.9	C15H25O3Si2	309.1337	-1.0	6.7	293.1035 (41) / 219.0852 / 172.9581(19)	<i>m</i> -Coumaric-2H+2TMS+H
343.1400	18.8	C15H27O5Si2	343.1392	-0.8	7.1	327.1126 (47) / 299.1528 (45) / 253.0907 (83) / 211.0791 (65)	Syringic acid-2H+2TMS+H
309.1333 (72)	20.0	C15H25O3Si2	309.1337	-0.4	11.2	293.1069 (42) / 219.0868 / 195.0848 (10)	<i>p</i> -Coumaric acid-2H+2TMS+H
459.1860	20.8	C19H39O5Si4	459.1869	0.9	4.6	415.2030 (13) / 369.1424 (11) / 327.1306 (13) / 239.0597 (5)	Gallic acid-4H+4TMS+H
339.1447 (61)	24.4	C16H27O4Si2	339.1442	-0.5	10.2	323.1124 (24) / 249.0967 / 177.0558 (10)	Ferulic acid-2H+2TMS+H
397.1680 (37)	25.8	C18H33O4Si3	397.1681	0.1	7.2	307.1232 / 172.9582 (22)	Caffeic acid-3H+3TMS+H
369.1546 (22)	28.7	C17H29O5Si2	369.1548	0.2	9.2	353.1244 (14) / 279.1084	Sinapinic acid-2H+2TMS+H
665.2635 (62)	49.9	C30H53O7Si5	665.2632	-0.3	18.3	593.2320 (11) / 297.1009 (10) / 225.0608 / 172.9581 (32)	Taxifolin-5H+5TMS
487.1792	54.5	C24H35O5Si3	487.1787	-0.5	9.2	415.1399 (9) / 193.0695 (7)	Apigenin-3H+3TMS+H
575.2142	58.7	C27H43O6Si4	575.2131	-1.1	6.4	503.1744 (9) / 281.1007 (10)	Luteolin-4H+4TMS+H
503.2283 (16)	60.0	C26H39O6Si2	503.2280	-0.3	15.2	485.2189 / 414.1686 (31) / 247.1154 (30)	Pinoresinol-2H+2TMS+H

Table 2

m/z signals of the main compounds identified in the isolated phenolic fractions.

In bold letter we highlight the prevalent ion in the MS spectrum for each compound. The relative intensity of the other m/z signals present in the MS spectra of the phenols is shown between brackets. *Most intense chromatographic peak in the isolated fraction.

Isolated fractions	Retention time (min)	Quasi-molecular ion				In-source fragmentation pattern	Possible compounds
		m/z experimental	Molecular formula	Error (mDa)	mSigma		
1	17.3*	315.1253 (3)	C14H23O6Si	0.5	5.1	283.2102 (37) / 225.1742 / 173.0415 (9) / 139.1161 (15)	EA-H+1TMS+H
	17.9	315.1267 (3)	C14H23O6Si	0.9	3.8	283.2091 (50) / 225.1728 / 173.0415 (20) / 139.1193 (16)	EA-H+1TMS+H (isomer)
	21.7	387.1668 (3)	C17H31O6Si2	1.4	4.8	355.1296 / 297.0831 (30) / 265.1965 (12) / 223.1753 (74) / 173.0413 (29)	EA-2H+2TMS+2H
2	16.6	MS signals observed: 429.2267 (4) / 361.2942 / 169.1580 (44)					
	16.8*	MS signals observed: 481.3377 (31) / 363.2745 / 273.2070 (39) / 149.1196 (18)					
3	41.8*	465.2122 (2)	C23H37O6Si2	0.1	6.2	447.3312 (4) / 375.2898 (6) / 281.2498 / 209.1942 (82)	DOA-2H+2TMS+H
	48.3	507.2284 (2)	C25H39O7Si2	-5.6	4.9	475.3426 (5) / 193.1953	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
4	10.8	MS signals observed: 193.1952					
	36.4	MS signals observed: 249.2699					
	44.5*	MS signal observed: 193.1951					Lig Agl-related comp
	48.3	507.2185 (2)	C25H39O7Si2	4.3	3.6	475.3422 (5) / 193.1949	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
5	44.7	MS signal observed: 193.1952					Lig Agl-related comp
	48.4	507.2185 (2)	C25H39O7Si2	4.3		475.3429 (5) / 193.1947	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
	68.0*	563.2445 (2)	C26H39O6Si2	2.5	8.3	545.3963 (7) / 527.3779 (2) / 474.3342 (3) / 337.2673 / 307.2522 (12) / 277.2357 (17)	Syringaresinol-2H+2TMS+H
6	36.9	377.1789 (1)	C20H29O5Si	-1.1	6.8	359.2882 / 193.1950	D-Lig Agl-H+1TMS+H
	47.0	507.2257 (2)	C25H39O7Si2	-2.9	6.5	475.3365 (5) / 193.1935	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H (isomer)
	48.5	507.2232 (2)	C25H39O7Si2	0.4	9.1	475.3359 (5) / 193.1944	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
	61.1*	561.2330 (2)	C28H41O8Si2	0.4	12.5	543.3710 (1) / 501.3554 (30) / 483.3417(10) / 472.3413 (1) / 305.2331 / 275.2165 (48)	Ac Pin-2H+2TMS
7	36.9	377.1742 (1)	C20H29O5Si	3.6	3.6	359.2935 / 193.1950	D-Lig Agl-H+1TMS+H
	48.5	507.2232 (2)	C25H39O7Si2	-0.4	15.2	475.3359 (5) / 193.1944	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
	49.7	523.2185 (1)	C25H39O8Si2	-0.8	11.1	281.2492 / 225.1673 (7) / 209.2006 (7)	Ol Agl-2H+2TMS+H
	52.5*	611.2528 (3)	C28H47O9Si3	0.6	15.6	579.3858 (1) / 313.2290 (12) / 281.2497 / 209.1933 (4) / 173.0419 (6)	10-hydroxy-Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H
8	47.8	523.2188 (1)	C25H39O8Si2	-1.1	11.1	313.2261 (9) / 193.1950 / 173.0411 (5)	H- Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
	49.7*	523.2188 (2)	C25H39O8Si2	-1.1	11.1	281.2492 / 225.1723 (7) / 209.1937 (7)	Ol Agl-2H+2TMS+H
	51.8	521.1987 (40)	C25H37O8Si2	3.4	8.5	281.2480 / 209.1939 (47)	Ol Agl-related comp
	53.1	595.2556 (3)	C28H47O8Si3	-0.8	6.9	563.3841 (4) / 281.2483	Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H
	53.8	625.3083 (6)	C30H53O8Si3	-4.0	8.5	593.3947 (6) / 281.2483	Ol Agl-related comp
9	44.7*	435.1830	C22H31O7Si	0.4	13.1	193.1966	Lig Agl-H+1TMS+H
	48.5	MS signal observed: 193.1965					Lig Agl-related comp

Table 3

m/z signals detected of the most relevant phenolic compounds present in the extract of extra-virgin olive oil. In bold letter we highlight the prevalent ion in the MS spectrum for each compound. The relative intensity of the other m/z signals present in the MS spectra of the phenols is shown between brackets.

MS signal (when no defined before)	Retention time (minutes)	Parent (precursor) ion isolated and further fragmented	MS/MS Fragmentation	Compounds
	10.0	193.1061	144.7203 (18) / 126.6961 (12) / 108.6209	Tyrosol-2H+2TMS
299.2632 / 281.2477 / 193.1613	13.4	193.1613	164.8823 (9) / 144.7197 (16) / 108.6199	Unknow
		281.2477	192.9426 (50) / 118.7576 / 105.6919 (69)	
		299.2632	266.9440 (10) / 192.9298	
	15.1	370.1754	267.0739 (5) / 192.9301 / 178.8886 (95)	Hydroxytyrosol-3H+3TMS
		281.2480	192.9304 / 165.8570 (54) / 114.7144 (27)	
	16.6	281.2469	192.9377 (73) / 148.7980 (67) / 118.7612 / 104.6898 (75)	Protocatechuic acid-3H+3TMS+H
	17.0	385.1642	178.8888 / 267.0723 (5)	Dopac-3H+3TMS+H
		267.0716	178.8913 / 148.7747 (81) / 108.6205 (17)	
		178.8913	148.7737	
	17.3	315.1253	283.0594 (54) / 224.9829 / 183.1515 (10) / 139.1157 (18)	Elenolic acid-H+1TMS+H
		224.9829	190.8610 (54) / 164.8771 / 118.6764 (41)	
		283.0595	132.8196 (76) / 118.6764 (96) / 104.6874 / 90.6075 (73)	
192.9661	33.3	192.9661	177.9179 (10) / 144.7184 (22) / 127.7065 (12) / 108.6197	
	36.9	192.9667	164.8792 (10) / 144.7203 (20) / 126.6961 (10) / 108.6209	D-Lig Agl-related comp
281.0971	38.4	281.0971	192.9426 (30) / 118.7612 (63) / 104.6892	Lig Agl-related comp
192.9717	40.0	192.9717	177.9152 (8) / 144.7196 (16) / 126.6981 (11) / 108.6201	Lig Agl-related comp
192.9717	40.9	192.9717	177.9152 (14) / 144.7196 (21) / 126.6981 (12) / 108.6201	Lig Agl-related comp
411.3288 / 281.0977 / 208.9862	42.0	411.3288	128.7833 / 72.4970 (36)	DOA-2H+2TMS+H
		281.0977	192.9331 / 168.8517 (52) / 90.6110 (16) / 72.4970 (56)	
		208.9862	190.9405 (79) / 164.8767 / 135.7303 (70) / 108.6181 (30)	
411.3288 / 281.0977 / 208.9862	42.2	411.3288	128.7833 / 72.4970 (36)	DOA-2H+2TMS+H
		281.0977	192.9331 / 168.8517 (62) / 90.6110 (19) / 72.4970 (65)	
		208.9862	190.9424 (83) / 164.8771 / 135.7294 (68) / 108.6234 (40) / 90.6110 (10)	
501.3843 / 411.4616	43.1	501.3843	128.7831 / 102.6687 (5) / 72.4960 (11)	Unknow
		411.4616	128.7831 / 94.6589 (12) / 72.4970 (45)	
	44.8	281.0971	192.9426 / 118.7612 (95) / 104.6892 (88)	Lig Agl-H+1TMS+H
537.2533 / 281.0968	45.8	281.0968	192.9426 / 118.7612 (95) / 104.6892 (82)	Methyl Ol Agl-2H+2TMS+H
553.2491 / 281.0975 / 192.9678	46.9	553.2491	281.0968 (46) / 192.9296 / 122.7343 (5)	H-D-Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H
		281.0975	192.9377 (75) / 148.7980 (80) / 118.7612 / 104.6898 (95)	
		192.9678	177.9152 (12) / 144.7196 (17) / 126.6981 (11) / 108.6211	
192.9717 / 462.2351	47.0	192.9717	177.9152 (12) / 144.7196 (17) / 126.6981 (11) / 108.6211	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
		462.2351	192.9622 / 177.9192 (13) / 97.6840 (9)	
	47.9	192.9718	177.9152 (11) / 144.7196 (20) / 126.6981 (10) / 108.6211	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H
		475.1989	192.9646 / 176.9046 (10) / 148.8093 (4) / 72.4060 (7)	
		297.0825	248.9216 (24) / 208.9031 (19) / 132.8241 (50) / 118.7593 / 104.6874 (78) / 90.6075 (31) / 72.4970 (12)	
	48.6	192.9665	177.9152 (8) / 144.7196 (18) / 126.6981 (10) / 108.6211	Lig Agl-2H+2TMS+H

MS signal (when no defined before)	Retention time (minutes)	Parent (precursor) ion isolated and further fragmented	MS fragments	Compounds
	49.8	523.2188	281.2492 (36) / 225.1733 (3) / 193.1593	Ol Agl-2H+2TMS+H
		281.4481	192.9304 / 165.8570 (60) / 114.7144 (25) / 90.6075 (11) / 72.4970 (48)	
550.2678 / 281.0973	51.8	550.2678	281.0971 (75) / 192.9302 / 177.9207 (16) / 165.0849 (9) / 97.6855 (9)	Ol Agl-related comp
		281.0973	192.9377 (48) / 148.7980 (83) / 118.7612 / 104.6898 (80)	
521.2068 / 281.0879 / 208.9912	51.9	521.2068	281.0971 (8) / 192.9302	Ol Agl-related comp
		281.0879	192.9377 (23) / 148.7980 (75) / 118.7612 / 104.6898 (95)	
		208.9912	190.9457 (68) / 178.9249 (46) / 164.8781 / 108.6224 (21)	
397.3832 / 160.9290	52.5	313.0876	142.8366 (27) / 132.8210 (52) / 118.7623 / 104.6888 (56) / 90.6088 (15)	10-hydroxy-Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H
		281.0981	192.9377 (90) / 148.7980 (64) / 118.7612 / 104.6898 (70) / 90.6075 (30) / 72.4970 (55)	
	53.3	595.2540	281.0975 (78) / 192.9300	Ol Agl-3H+3TMS+H
		563.2299	281.0960 (42) / 192.9300	
		297.0929	266.9500 (21) / 224.9536 (23) / 192.9335 (41) / 118.7611 / 104.6895 (67) / 90.6055 (21)	
	53.9	281.0978	192.9377 / 148.7980 (31) / 118.7612 (24) / 104.6898 (42)	Ol Agl-related comp
		281.0975	192.9649 (47) / 178.9214 (58) / 154.8671 (90) / 118.7611 / 104.6895 (90) / 90.6055 (29)	
	54.0	281.0975	192.9649 (68) / 178.9214 (52) / 154.8671 (90) / 118.7611 / 104.6895 (95) / 90.6055 (25)	Ol Agl-related comp
	54.5	487.1792	471.1498 / 399.1083 (30) / 415.1399 (10) / 193.0695 (10)	Apigenin-3H+3TMS+H
	58.7	575.2142	559.3394 / 487.2883 (5) / 297.2119 (4)	Luteolin-4H+4TMS+H
		503.3205	431.2735 (28) / 415.2367 (29) / 225.1546 (38) / 191.1419	
	59.9	503.2274	367.2070 (35) / 354.1982 / 179.1393 (96)	Pinoresinol-2H+2TMS+H
		485.3569	414.3040 (10) / 384.1199 (88) / 289.2369 (3) / 259.0503 (35) / 208.9846 / 178.8874 (30) / 128.7817 (61)	
		414.1698	354.0687 (90) / 146.8805 (45) / 118.7618	
	60.2	247.0525	201.9547 (53) / 177.9131 (82) / 164.8770 / 127.7674 (42)	Unknow
397.3832		160.9312 (46) / 146.8805 / 132.8342 (58) / 118.7614 (74) / 104.6907 (56)		
61.1	160.9290	127.7686 (73) / 114.7141 / 90.6062 (50)	Ac Pin-2H+2TMS	
	501.2143	275.0644 (14) / 247.0429 (15) / 222.9837 / 208.9865 (31)		
	305.0929	228.9791 (74) / 216.9663 / 202.9288 (38) / 114.7153 (95) / 72.4960 (21)		
	276.0701	216.9666 (73) / 202.9288 (47) / 114.7153 / 72.4960 (19)		
	259.0576	228.9806 / 202.9288 (31) / 198.8934 (38) / 104.6901 (10)		
68.0	503.2283	337.2673 / 238.9865 (10)	Syringaresinol-2H+2TMS+H	

Table 4

Analytical parameters of the GC-APCI-MaXis MS method.

<i>Analytes</i>	<i>LOD (ppm)</i>	<i>Ions used quantification</i>	<i>LOQ (ppm)</i>	<i>Linearity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)</i>	<i>Calibration curves^a</i>	<i>r²</i>	<i>Repeat. Intra-day^b</i>	<i>Repeat. Inter-day^b</i>	<i>Accuracy^c</i>	<i>Response factor (neat solution)^{d, e}</i>	<i>Response factor (with matrix)^{d, e}</i>
<i>Tyrosol</i>	0.40	193.1061	1.33	LOQ-100	$y = 29080x - 135585$	0.987	1.53	4.16	97.7	25.1	24.0
<i>Hydroxytyrosol</i>	0.21	281.1410	0.70	LOQ-50	$y = 5809x - 6690$	0.994	1.61	4.10	95.4	5.8	5.5
<i>Homovanillic acid</i>	1.01	209.1007	3.37	LOQ-100	$y = 4650x - 17309$	0.994	1.30	3.76	97.3	4.0	3.8
<i>p-coumaric acid</i>	0.19	219.0868	0.63	LOQ-100	$y = 6649x - 13911$	0.994	0.89	3.67	99.1	6.6	6.9
<i>Ferulic acid</i>	0.19	249.0967	0.63	LOQ-100	$y = 7313x - 33576$	0.985	0.73	6.01	98.6	7.3	7.2
<i>Luteolin</i>	1.05	575.2142	0.32	LOQ-50	$y = 22182x - 14950$	0.993	1.77	6.07	101.5	22.7	23.7
<i>Apigenin</i>	0.63	487.1792	2.10	LOQ-100	$y = 3223x - 24031$	0.998	1.45	4.74	100.5	3.2	3.0
<i>Pinoresinol</i>	0.13	485.2189	0.43	LOQ-100	$y = 2657x - 18999$	0.993	1.03	5.01	98.2	2.6	2.5

^a A (peak area) = $a + b \times C$ (ppm) for ten points (n=5).

^bRSDs values (%) for peak areas corresponding to each compound; measured from three injections of each analyte within the same day (intra-) and on three different days (inter-).

^cThe accuracy of the assay is the closeness of the test value obtained to the nominal value. It is calculated by determining trueness and precision. (%Recovery, %RSD).

^dRF was defined as the ratio between peak area and concentration of the analyte. Peak area values were multiplied by 10^{-3} to express the RF values with less significant figures.

^eCoefficient of variation (%) was in every cases lower than 4.8%.

Table 5**Quantitative overview of phenolic compounds in the extra-VOO.**

Data given in mg/kg or area (when pure standards were not available); n=3

(Value shown = mean value). RSD in all the cases $\leq 5\%$.

Recoveries described by Gómez-Caravaca et al. [33] were applied the quantitative calculations.

Analyte	t_r (min) (run 2)	Picual-Arbequina oil		Frantoio oil		Hojiblanca oil	
		Area	mg/kg	Area	mg/kg	Area	mg/kg
Tyrosol ^a	7.2	3.33		1.67		7.21	
Hydroxytyrosol ^b	12.3	8.31		2.42		9.32	
Protocatechuic acid ^c	13.6	0.25		n.d.		0.21	
Dopac	14.1	Internal standard (IS)					
		Area	mg/kg	Area	mg/kg	Area	mg/kg
Elenolic acid ^{b,d}	14.2	356567	4.42	936997	11.62	228073	2.82
D-Lig Agl ^{a,d}	25.6	1460407	6.55	182971	0.82	821396	3.68
Lig Agl-related comp ^{a,d}	27.6	103272	0.46	68637	0.30	203280	0.91
Lig Agl-related comp ^{a,d}	28.3	49646	0.22	n.d.	n.d.	148478	0.67
DOA ^{b,d}	29.2	1029476	12.76	276124	3.42	422605	5.24
501.3843 / 411.3312 ^{b,d}	30.0	167040	2.07	43682	0.54	92022	1.14
Lig Agl ^{a,d}	31.2	830890	3.72	172235	0.77	151760	0.68
Methyl Ol Agl ^{b,d}	32.0	56047	0.69	16797	0.21	n.d.	n.d.
H-D-Ol Agl ^{b,d}	32.8	211872	2.63	219061	2.72	33328	0.41
Lig Agl ^{a,d}	34.2	3907685	17.52	3962249	17.76	1334142	5.98
Ol Agl ^{b,d}	35.3	3713714	46.04	n.d.	n.d.	183453	2.27
Ol Agl-related comp ^{b,d}	37.0	540608	6.70	n.d.	n.d.	25417	0.32
10-H-Ol Agl ^{b,d}	37.6	429370	5.32	n.d.	n.d.	124260	1.54
Ol Agl ^{b,d}	38.3	2209565	27.40	n.d.	n.d.	304794	3.78
Apigenin ^e	39.2	0.35		0.19		0.20	
Luteolin ^f	42.9	1.65		n.d.		n.d.	
Pinosresinol ^g	43.8	3.25		0.75		0.54	
Ac Pin ^g	44.6	19.37		25.45		n.d.	

^a: quantified with the calibration curve of tyrosol.^b: quantified with the calibration curve of hydroxytyrosol.^c: quantified with the calibration curve of protocatechuic acid.^d: semi-quantitative information (mean value of area of the compound). Pure standards were not available.^e: quantified with the calibration curve of apigenin.^f: quantified with the calibration curve of luteolin.^g: quantified with the calibration curve of pinosresinol.

n.d.: non detected